

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ENHANCING THE BUDGET CONTROL ON FINDING SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROJECTS IN REGION BY PARTICIPATION OF THE CITIZEN IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The scientific article analyzes the funds spent from the state budget for the financing of socio-economic development programs of regions in Uzbekistan and their control. In order to increase the destination of the funds spent on the socio-economic development of the regions, proposals on the participation of the population have been developed.

Keywords: Government budget, local budgets, expenses of the local budgets, socio-economic development of the regions, transparency of the budget, budget control, citizen participation (participatory budget).

INTRODUCTION

At the last decades of the century, attention is being paid to increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of providing funds for the socio-economic development programs of the regions. According to the information of the Asian Development Bank, "Developed countries will spend 33 billion dollars or 6.8% of GDP annually on the goals of improving the infrastructure of the regions of the USA, Central Europe and Asian countries, which will serve to meet the infrastructure requirements of the regions until 2030»1.

Proportionate use of the financial resources of the republican and local budgets, which are spent on timely and continuous provision of socio-economic development programs of the regions, public control is of special importance in the regular control of their effectiveness.

Scientific research is being carried out in such directions as ensuring the transparency of the funds spent on the financing of the socio-economic development programs of the regions, giving priority to the use of the remaining part of the tax revenues at the disposal of the local budgets by creating infrastructure for small business entities in the regions, and expanding industrial production.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the funds spent on socio-economic development of regions in Uzbekistan, their control, especially the state of public control, and to develop scientific proposals and practical recommendations.

Key findings of the scientific article are followings:

To ensure the transparency of the funds spent on the financing of the socio-economic development programs of the regions, to achieve the effectiveness of the budget funds by announcing them in quarterly periodicals;

It has been proven that the transparency of financing is ensured by publishing information on the funds spent on regional programs in periodicals.

MAIN PART

Local budgets are one of the main tools for delivering the products of multi-level redistribution of national income to the population. To a certain extent, the local budgets finance the expenses of local production sectors, communal economy, improvement of the territory, and a number of other sectors and sectors that provide services that ensure the normal life activity of the general population.

Local budgets are the relevant regional, district, city funds of the state budget and are an important link of the two-tier budget system in Uzbekistan. The socio-economic nature of local budgets is reflected in its functions. The following can be noted about them:

- formation of monetary funds that form the financial basis of the activities of local state administration bodies;
- redistribution and use of monetary funds between regional economic sectors and social sectors;
- control over the financial and economic activities of enterprises, organizations and institutions subordinated to local state administration.

The emergence of local budgets and their expenses in Central Asia dates back to the middle of the first millennium BC. During this period, the Ahmonites ruled the territory of Central Asia and occupied a very large territory, and the territories were divided into satrapies. During the Achaemenid era, the territory of Central Asia was divided into 4 satrapies, and each satrapy paid a tax of 1100 talents annually².

The classic model of the administration system in Central Asia was put forward by Ismail Somoni, and Ismail Somoni, summarizing the experience of previous dynasties, formed an advanced system, that is, management according to this system consisted of a supreme ruler's dargah and a set of devans. All 10 existing ministries obeyed the supreme ruler's dargah. The devans had local branches that obeyed the central ministry as well as the local governments. Hundreds of administrative staff and mirzas were employed in these

1 <https://adbi.us12.list-manage.com/track/click?u=7300634262c7cc5dc58dcd5e3&iid=5e64c53c34&e=bbb935aa1>

2 H.Sobirov History of the Public Finance of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: “Таълим манбаи” Publishing House, 2002. – P.11

dewans and their local offices. They were paid salaries from central and local officials in the prescribed manner³.

Taking into account the above-mentioned features, it can be concluded that state and local expenses in Central Asia are grouped as follows:

- maintenance costs of the supreme ruler's dargah and the dargahs serving it;
- expenses of troops and sepoys;
- expenses related to science and cultural activities;
- other expenses.

Amir Temur was the great leader, and during the Timurid period, all expenses can be said to be divided into five groups:

- General expenses of the administrative office and palace kingdom;
- Military and military expenses;
- Expenditures aimed at improving the development of the country and the welfare of the country;
 - Expenses related to science, culture and religious activities;
 - Social protection and other expenses⁴.

During the reign of Amir Temur, taking into account the complexity of managing the finances of 27 occupied countries from one center, taking over the funding of all regional courts and events from the central treasury, Amir Temur entrusted the management of regions to governors and ministers.

Timur did not centralize the administrative costs of 27 countries, but gave the right to collect taxes to local bodies. At the same time, he recommended and supervised the recording of all expenses and income in the form of income and expenditure estimates⁵.

Summarizing the above-mentioned opinions, the initial attempts to determine one or another expenses were made a long time ago, and in these processes, the governing bodies of the administrative regions were required to be within the norms established by the law. Also, the amount of general expenses should be determined in relation to the national income; in the form of correct association of separate cost groups with the amount of services provided; as a result, the types of costs are generally determined by comparing the relative importance of the quantity and quality of the services provided at the expense of these cost items.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the classical economist A. Smith, "expenses that represent the importance of districts and cities should be reflected in the expenses of the district or regional budget... and must be covered from district and city revenues, and should not be covered by diverting funds from the general income of the society"⁶.

A. Wildavsky tried to create a theory of effective use of the budget in the USA. According to him, the theory of the effectiveness of the budget process describes the nature of the relationship between its participants; it is important to popularize the success of the participants of the budget process, to achieve budget management decisions based on the effectiveness of strategies⁷.

Local economists T. Malikov and N. Khaydarov defined "Budget expenses as expenses incurred by the state in connection with the performance of its functions and tasks.

According to local economist A. Islamkulov, "in order to perform their functions in the regions, local state authorities should have an appropriate financial base, that is, we are talking about local budgets." Local budget funds are directed to finance economic, social, cultural programs and other events of local significance⁸.

METHODOLOGY

In the scientific article, empirical research methods were used to summarize, analyze and evaluate the data of several years, and to evaluate the dynamics of data changes in the last 5 years in Surkhandarya region.

DATA ANALYSIS

In modern conditions, special attention is paid to the industrialization of the economy in the further development and liberalization of the economy of Uzbekistan. Establishing an industrialized economy in the country, creating an added value chain through the transition from existing raw materials and resources to the production of finished and semi-finished products, creating permanent jobs for the population will ultimately provide an opportunity to become the owner of a stable income. This strategic task will be implemented in the territories of the republic, resulting in an increase in the share of industrial products per capita.

Depending on the level of socio-economic development of the region, more or less financial flows (investments) may be attracted to this region. Therefore, the living conditions of the population in the regions, the conditions created for starting a business, as a result of ensuring the expansion of the flow of financial resources, the speed of their movement, provide a stable income base of the local budgets and the continuous financing of the state's provision of social benefits to the population in the region, or vice versa. At the same time, this aspect reveals the nature of the competition phenomenon of the region.

We will analysis the projects and their financing from the local budget of Surkhandarya region within the framework of the state investment program.

3 H.Sobirov History of the Public Finance of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: “Таълим манбаи” Publishing House, 2002. – P.13.

4 H.Sobirov History of the Public Finance of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: “Таълим манбаи” Publishing House, 2002. – Pp.41-42

5 H.Sobirov History of the Public Finance of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: “Таълим манбаи” Publishing House, 2002. – P.44

6 Adam Smith Inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nation.

7 Wildavsky, A. (1966). The Political Economy of Efficiency: Cost-Benefit Analysis, Systems Analysis, and Program Budgeting. *Public Administration Review*, 26(4), 292–310. <https://doi.org/10.2307/973301>

8 Islamkulov A.Kh. Fiscal policy aimed at ensuring the equivalency of the budget in the medium term in Uzbekistan // *Open Access Peer-reviewed Journal Science Review* 9(26), November 2019. – Pp.3-6. IndexCopernicus (GIF - **85.90**) DOI: https://doi.org/10.31435/rsglobal_sr

Fig.1. The dynamics of the growth of projects and their amount under the state investment program implemented in Surkhandarya region⁹

According to the data of Figure 1, the total cost of 99 projects in Surkhandarya region, the southern region of the republic, in 2018 319.5 billion soums were implemented, in 2019 170 projects for 451.3 billion soums, in 2020 94 projects for 422.0 billion soums, in 2021 135 projects for 1,238.6 billion soums, in 2022 140 projects for 685.5 billion soums million soums. In general, in 2022, compared to 2021, the amount of funds allocated from the local budget decreased, but the number of projects increased.

In conclusion, it is of particular importance to strengthen public participation and control in the implementation of these investment projects. We will analyze the cases implemented in Uzbekistan in this direction.

Since 2019 in Uzbekistan, citizens began to participate in the distribution of state budget funds, that is, a mechanism was introduced that provides for the allocation of at least 10 percent of the additional resources of district (city) budgets to activities formed on the basis of public opinion. The information publication "Budget for Citizens", developed annually by the Ministry of Finance, was published for public discussion, and the "Open Budget" information portal (www.openbudget.uz) was launched.

When commenting on budget transparency, it is worth noting that "The International Budget Partnership (IBP) standard of the International Budget Partnership (IBP) was established in 1997. Budget transparency is a tool for improving governance and reducing global poverty. Budget process transparency and emphasizes the importance of the Government's responsibility to him. This standard is aimed at citizens and civil society and includes:

1. Strengthening the skills and knowledge of civil society organizations located in the country;
2. Study and monitor the state of budget transparency, participation and accountability worldwide;
3. It involves working with international stakeholders to encourage citizen engagement in budget matters and creating an environment to communicate government's progress in openness, as well as strategic and effective practices.

Adherence to this standard Governments will conduct an open budget survey every two years starting in 2006. These questionnaires focus on three specific aspects.

Fig.2. Aspects of the The International Budget Partnership (IBP)) Standart¹⁰

⁹ Муаллиф ишланмаси (Сурхондарё вилоят Иқтисодиёт ва молия бош бошқармаси ҳисобот маълумотлари асосида).

According to Figure 4, budget transparency focuses on the openness, timeliness and completeness of the 8 main budget documents to the public, their organization based on the general criteria accepted in the international experience in state financial management, and the announcement of the budget process. This section of the study is used to calculate the "Open budget index". Countries are given a score from 0 to 100 and are ranked according to their level of fiscal transparency. Budget Participation – Governments contribute to decision-making on the collection and spending of public resources by allowing civil society and the general public to participate in the budget process; Budget control means regular monitoring of collection and spending of financial resources (independent fiscal institutions, legislative bodies and supreme audit institutions) to the state budget.

In my opinion, citizen participation in the budget process and budget transparency will provide the government with clear guidelines for budgeting and suggestions on how to resolve the often encountered difficulties in this process. For this purpose, it would be appropriate to increase the financial literacy of the population, to develop guidelines that help citizens to understand the budget in a simple language, and to organize explanations with specific examples.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research conducted as a result of achieving the goal of the scientific article, the following conclusions were formed:

the governing bodies of the administrative regions were required to be within the norms established by the law;

the amount of general expenses should be determined in relation to the national income;

there are no clear, unified scientific-theoretical approaches to local budget spending powers;

to strengthen public participation and control in the implementation of these investment projects;

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